

Physico-Chemical Studies on the Binding of Metal Ions with Soybean Protein. Part III. Polarographic Studies with Zn^{++} and Cd^{++}

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The effect of the soybean protein concentration on the limiting current of Zn^{++} and Cd^{++} has been studied at different pH values. It was found that the value of i_d/i_{d_0} decreases with the increase in the concentration of the protein at a fixed pH. However, the value increases on adding varying amounts of metal ions to a fixed amount of the protein. Log K values computed from the polarographic data show that Zn^{++} is more strongly bound than Cd^{++} with the carboxyl as well as the imidazole group of the protein.

RECENTLY¹⁻² polarographic analysis has been employed in investigating metal complexes of simple organic substances, amino acids and peptides. In these investigations the reduction waves of metal ions have been found to be influenced by protein in two ways; firstly, the suppression of maxima, if any, and secondly, marked decrease in diffusion current. For the latter number of factors, viz., adsorption of protein on Hg-drop³⁻⁴, increase in viscosity⁵ and complex formation³⁻⁴ have been reasoned out.

The conventional polarographic method based on the shifts in $E_{1/2}$ is not suitable for determining metal protein complexes because the shifts are too small to ensure accurate determination. Tanford⁶⁻⁷ proposed a method based upon changes in diffusion current of the metal in presence of protein for investigating metal protein complexes. According to him such factors like adsorption and viscosity do not appreciably affect the diffusion current provided suitable pH and concentration conditions are maintained, then the ratio of i_d/i_{d_0} can be taken as a measure of the extent of binding of the metal to the protein. Tanford and coworkers⁸⁻⁹ and later Malik and coworkers¹⁰⁻¹¹ have successfully employed the above technique to the binding of a number of metals to fibrillar protein. We have now extended these studies to vegetable proteins. The results of our studies on the binding of Zn^{++} and Cd^{++} to soybean are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: Soybean protein used in these studies was prepared by the method of Suminokura¹². The soybean meal (B.D.H.) was dehulled and defatted with petroleum ether. The defatted meal was extracted several times with $N/20$ KOH and finally precipitated with dil. HCl at pH 4.90. The precipitates were purified by

redissolving and reprecipitating at the same pH. The sample obtained was washed thoroughly with distilled water until free from chloride. It may be mentioned that glycinin is the only fraction which is precipitated at pH 4.9 out of main three components glycinin, glutelin and phasoeolin present in soybean.

Anal. R samples of zinc sulphate and cadmium sulphate were dissolved in distilled water and the metal content of the solutions were estimated by complexometric titration¹³ using EDTA as titrant and Eriochrome black T and Xylenol orange as indicators. Acetate buffer of pH 5.57 and NH_4OH-NH_4Cl buffer of pH 7.5, 8.3, 9.4 and 10.5 were prepared by the usual methods of preparation of buffers.

Apparatus: Heyrovsky polarograph model LP55 in conjunction with a multiflex galvanometer was used manually for recording the polarograms. H-shaped cell was employed since it was found to be most suitable for deaeration of protein solution without denaturation. Pure N_2 was passed for 20 mins in each case to remove dissolved oxygen. All the measurements were made by keeping the cell at constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The drop time was 3.5 sec/drop with the rate of flow of 2.2 mg/sec., at $h = 55$ cms. The pH of the buffers and mixture of metal protein solution were measured with Cambridge pH-meter.

Procedure: The following sets were prepared.

- (i) 1.0 ml of $ZnSO_4$ (0.01M), 0.5 ml of $CdSO_4$ (0.01M); 5.0 ml of buffers of pH (5.57, 7.5, 8.3, 9.4 and 10.5); 3.0 ml of 2.0% protein solution were mixed and the total was made upto 12.0 ml by adding 1.0M KCl solution and water (to keep ionic strength constant at 0.15).
- (ii) Similar set as in (i) were prepared by mixing water instead of protein.

(iii) Varying amounts of protein were mixed with 1.0 ml of $ZnSO_4$ or $CdSO_4$ and 5.0 ml buffer (pH 5.57). Total was made upto to 12.0 ml by adding requisite amount of KCl and H_2O .

(iv) Varying amounts of metal ions (0.10, 0.25, 0.50, 1.25, 1.50 mM) were mixed with a fixed amount (30 ml) of soybean protein solution and 5.0 ml of buffer. The total was made upto 12.0 ml as under (i).

(v) Similar sets as in (iv) were prepared without adding the protein.

Fig. 1. Some typical polarograms of metal ions with and without protein :

- (1) 1.0 mM Zn^{++}
- (2) 1.0 mM Zn^{++} with 0.6% Soybean
- (3) 1.0 mM Zn^{++} with 3.0 ml of 1.2% Soybean
- (4) 1.5 mM Zn^{++}
- (5) 1.5 mM Zn^{++} with 3.0 ml of 2.0% Soybean
- (6) 1.25 mM Cd^{++}
- (7) 1.25 mM Cd^{++} + 3.0 ml of 2.0% Soybean
- (8) 0.5 mM Cd^{++} at pH 5.57 with 1.0 ml of 0.5% Soybean
- (9) 0.5 mM Cd^{++} with 3.0 ml of 1.0% Soybean at pH 5.57.

Results and Discussion

Some typical polarograms are shown in Fig. 1. The nature of the waves was tested by Tomes's method¹⁴ and were found to be reversible.

The changes in the i_d/i_{d_0} at different pH for Zn^{++} +soybean and Cd^{++} +soybean system are shown in Fig. 2a; and the effect of protein concentration and metal concentration on i_d/i_{d_0} are represented in Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c respectively. These provide essential information regarding the binding of metal ion with proteins⁶⁻⁷.

According to Tanford's equation,

$$i_d/i_{d_0} = \frac{C_F + K'C_b}{C_0}$$

where C_F , C_b and C_0 are the free bound and original concentrations of the metal ions K' is the fractional coefficient and can be evaluated from the

Fig. 2.

limiting value of i_d from the plots of i_d/i_{d_0} vs pH (Fig. 2a). This equation forms the basis of theoretical and experimental checking of the results. It has been found that the discrepancy between theoretical and experimental results are less than 1.0%.

The value of V_M is obtained by the relation

$$V_M = C_b/P,$$

where P is the total molar concentration of protein. The molecular weight of soybean has been taken to be 1,00,000. The plots of V_M against pH show that the curve for Zn^{++} lies above that of Cd^{++} . This shows that Zn^{++} is bound to a slightly stronger extent than Cd^{++} to soybean protein (Fig. 2d). Furthermore a constancy in V_M is observed beyond pH 9.5. This probably indicates that the imidazole group of the soybean is more effectively bound with the metal ion than the carboxyl group. Cd^{++} +soybean system follows the similar observation as that of the Zn^{++} +soybean system.

The intrinsic constant K has been calculated by Scatchard's equation¹⁵

$$K = \frac{V_M}{(n - V_M - V_H)C_F}$$

The log K values for metal carboxyl interaction were found somewhat higher than the log K of Zn^{++} -acetate and Cd^{++} -acetate complexes (vide Table 1). At pH higher than 5.57, the imidazole groups from histidine residues lose their protons and thus, will be available for binding. The decrease in diffusion current with increase in pH provide, neglecting any possible effect of anion of buffer in supporting electrolyte, clear evidence for the interaction of the metal ion with the imidazole group of the protein. The log K values of Zn and Cd glycinin of soybean protein system from present study resemble closely the first association constant of Zn-imidazole and Cd-imidazole system (2.58 and 2.80).

TABLE I—COMPARISON OF LOG K VALUES FOR DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

Ligand	Method	log K Carboxyl group		log K Imidazole group	
		Zn ⁺⁺	Cd ⁺⁺	Zn ⁺⁺	Cd ⁺⁺
Soybean	Polarography	1.92	1.85	2.81	2.77
	Equilibrium dialysis.	1.86	—	2.86	—
Acetate	—	1.03	1.30	—	—
Imidazole	—	—	—	2.58	2.80

On the basis of the above studies it can be concluded that Zn^{++} is bound to a slightly stronger extent than Cd^{++} with both the carboxyl and the imidazole group of the soybean protein.

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